

Forecasting Holiday Travel Propensity using Markov Chains

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Purpose

The purpose of this paper is to show how Markov chains can be used as an additional forecasting source.

Design/methodology/approach

Holiday Travel Propensity (HTP) can be seen as a Markov process, so that the transitions from taking or not taking a holiday travel in one year into taking or not taking a holiday in the subsequent year are modeled. As opposed to other papers which made use of the Markov chain approach, this paper models holiday travel propensity from a source market perspective and shows how to integrate influencing factors (age, health status) and linear regression analysis into the Markov chain approach.

Findings

Markov processes will reach an equilibrium (Steady state) if transition rates are stable. Although this is not perfectly the case in Germany during the last eleven years, an HTP equilibrium of slightly less than 80% can be estimated. In general, the transition rates from taking a holiday travel in one year into taking a holiday travel in the subsequent year grew by approximately 0.22 percentage points per year over the last decade, while transition rates from not taking a holiday travel in one year into taking a holiday travel in the subsequent year fell by approximately 0.75 percentage points per year.

Analyzing transition rates in different age groups reveals that in older groups (60 years and older) equilibrium values are falling over time although actual HTP values are still on the rise. This might be an indicator that growth potential (in terms of participation) is lower for the older age groups compared to the younger groups. Furthermore, in the oldest group actual HTP values are slightly above the equilibrium, while in all other groups actual HTP values are below equilibrium. Same goes for people with poor health status. This might be an additional indicator that in those two groups (oldest, poor health) equilibrium has been reached, even if we take into consideration that these two indicators are correlated.

Taking the same model one step further we can also derive equilibrium values for the group of intensive holiday travelers (taking two or more holidays per year). For this group, the equilibrium is at 19% of the German population.

Research implications

From a research perspective, the paper shows one of the main advantages of Markov chain transition analyses compared to other forecasting methods. This advantage is the integrated predictive value which makes it possible to derive steady state levels with very little prior knowledge. Time series analysis, in this paper in the form of a simple linear regression model, can however improve the assessment of the results.

Practical implications

From a more practical point of view, the paper shows that Markov chains are a relatively straightforward and efficient way of deriving predictive value from survey data. The paper also points out the limitations of the method, making it particularly suitable as an additional method requiring only very moderate analytical effort.

Originality/value

The paper shows the basic principle of Markov chain transition analysis and its applicability to real tourism data, so that access to the methodology for researchers and the industry can be facilitated. It shows the combination of Markov chains and time series regression models. For the German market, it gives estimates for the steady state in terms on holiday travel participation and shows ways to identify segments with market potential.

Keywords

Holiday travel, Markov chain, Forecasting, Market potential

1 MARKOV CHAINS AND TOURISM FORECASTING METHODS

In their basic handbook on tourism forecasting, commissioned by the World Tourism Organization and the European Travel Commission, Simpson & Ladle (2008) introduce ten different sets of forecasting methodologies, among them time series based quantitative methods (from simple extrapolation and moving averages to simple regression, multiple regression and structural econometric models) and qualitative methods (among them Jury of Executive Opinion, Delphi Method and Scenario Planning). They end up in assessing causal (econometric) models as the premium methodology for forecasting. In line with this assessment, most of the research literature in the field concentrates on this family of methodologies, going back to the 1970s (Geurts, Buchman & Ibrahim 1976, Uysal & Crompton 1985, Smeral, Witt & Witt 1992) and even further. In their comprehensive review, Li, Song & Witt (2005) identified 420 studies on the topic of tourism demand modelling and forecasting during the period 1960-2002, and several authors have reviewed the economic modelling approaches within this timeframe (e.g. Crouch 1994, Witt & Witt 1995, Lim 1999) and beyond (Song et al. 2008).

In their literature review, Song & Li (2008) assessed 121 studies in the field, published in the period from 2000-2007. In these studies, a total of 45 different methods has been used, ranging from “ADLM: autoregressive distributed lag model” through “VECM: vector error correction mode”. They found, that in time series based models the ARMA family (autoregression moving average and its extensions like integrated, multivariate or seasonal ARMA) was the most popular, applied in over two thirds of the studies under review. In the second set of approaches (econometric causal modelling), the distribution of models used shows more variability, and some authors even count simple regression models as “causal methods” (Frechtling 2001).

In addition to quantitative time series based models (like the ARMA family) or causal models (like the linear structural relationship analysis), qualitative approaches like Delphi studies (von Bergner & Lohmann 2014) or scenario planning (Postma 2014) are in use.

Obviously, there is no lack of forecasting methods, not even in tourism research. This paper will assess whether Markov chains can be used to obtain additional information not available through other approaches. For already a long time, Markov chains are being discussed in academic research (cf. the comprehensive monographs by Behrends 2000, Brémaud 1999). They are used for industry solutions (e.g. the popular “predictive text” input methods on mobile phones) or even to identify the writer of a given text (Khmelev & Tweedie 2001). However, in tourism research, few applications can be found. Some studies used the Markov chain approach to estimate destination choice probabilities or the probability of returning customers (Mednick 1975, Beaman, Huan & Kozak 2001, Wang 2004, Choi, Mok & Han 2010), others (Xia, Zeepongsekul & Arrowsmith 2009, Xia, Zeepongsekul, & Packer 2010) used Markov chains to model spatio-temporal movements of tourists. One recent study (Tsionas & Assaf 2014) used an expansion of the method described in this paper (Markov chains based Monte Carlo method).

The Markov chain transition analysis discussed in this paper is a strictly quantitative method. In its basic form it is used for transitions from one period to the next for two states of an entity. The paper shows that already this basic approach can be applied to estimate a system equilibrium (steady state) using empirical data from more than 70,000 interviews collected during the last decade. The approach will then be enlarged by using time series regression models to provide better input and to better interpret output of such transition analyses. Furthermore, a breakdown into consumer segments will show that it is possible to estimate market potentials using Markov chains and how steady states for more than two transition groups can be derived.

The approach presented in this paper is of very moderate mathematical or modelling complexity. It can therefore hardly compete with or even replace other approaches. However, it is one objective of this paper to show that this method can give additional information on expected steady states that can otherwise only be obtained through rather complex models relying on large datasets.

A second objective is to actually give an estimate on a steady state of holiday travel propensity for the German market. And thirdly, it is one objective to show that transition analysis using Markov chains is a quite easy and attainable method not only for researchers, but also for the travel and tourism industry.

2 MARKOV CHAINS

2.1 General mechanics of Markov chains

A Markov chain¹ as a special instance of Markov processes describes the transition of a set of states of an entity in period t into a set of states in period $t+1$. Technically, Markov chains are processes with discrete time steps (Behrends 2000, Brémaud 1999, Seriola 2013). Their handling requires only some basic knowledge of linear algebra (cf. to Gantmacher 1960 or Waner & Costenoble 2013 for further mathematical background).

We assess the basic functioning by use of an example: A population (“entity”) can have two “states” in period t : having made a holiday travel in year t (“Holiday Traveler in t ”, $HT(t)$) or not having made a holiday travel in year t (“Non Traveler in t ”, $NT(t)$). A Markov process describes the transition of those having made a holiday travel in year t into the state of having made a holiday travel in year $t+1$ ($HT(t+1)$) or not having made a holiday travel in year $t+1$ ($NT(t+1)$). Both transitions add up to 1: All holiday travelers in t will be either holiday travelers or non-travelers in $t+1$. Equally, it describes the transition from non-travelers in t into the state of being holiday travelers in $t+1$ ($HT(t+1)$) or non-travelers in $t+1$ ($NT(t+1)$).

More formally, Markov chains can be seen as matrices of transition rates in t multiplied with actual shares of the states in t resulting in the share of states in period $t+1$.

$$(Eq. 1) \quad \begin{bmatrix} T1(HT \rightarrow HT) & T2(NT \rightarrow HT) \\ T3(HT \rightarrow NT) & T4(NT \rightarrow NT) \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} HT(t) \\ NT(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} HT(t+1) \\ NT(t+1) \end{bmatrix}$$

HT = Holiday Travelers

NT= Non Travelers (= 1 - HT)

T = Transition rate, e.g. $T1(HT \rightarrow NT)$ = Transition rate from Holiday Traveler in t to Non Traveler in $t+1$

Multiplying matrices simply implies taking the values of a row in t and multiply it with the column, resulting in the value for the row in $t+1$.

Example (Figure 1): In t there are 60% Holiday Travelers (HT) and 40% Non Travelers (NT). If of all Holiday Travelers in period t , 70% will take a holiday travel in period $t+1$ and 30% will not and if of all Non Travelers in period t , 15% will take a holiday travel in $t+1$ and 85% will not, then the resulting proportions in the next period will be 48% HT and 52% NT.

¹ named after the Russian mathematician Andrei Andreyevich Markov (1856-1922)

[Figure 1 about here]

More formally, the rate of Holiday Travelers in period $t+1$ will be calculated as:

$$(Eq. 2) \quad (0.70 * 0.60) + (0.15 * 0.40) = 0.48$$

In analogy, the rate of Non Travelers will be computed again as row values multiplied with the column:

$$(Eq. 3) \quad (0.30 * 0.60) + (0.85 * 0.40) = 0.52$$

2.2 Finding a steady state

It can be shown that a well-defined equilibrium (steady state) exists for every Markov process that has a square matrix, discrete states, stable transition rates (constant probabilities), a groupwise sum of transition rates of 1 and no deterministic cycles (Brémaud 1999). The steady state is where a given state in one period (e.g. the rate of holiday travelers in t) leads to exactly the same state in the next period (e.g. the rate of holiday travelers in $t+1$).

In our example, for the steady state calculation we search for that exact rate of Holiday Travelers which, multiplied with the transition matrix, gives us exactly the same rate of Holiday Travelers back in the next period. Because $NT = 1-HT$, we can write:

$$(Eq. 4) \quad HT(t + 1) = HT(t) * T1(HT \rightarrow HT) + (1 - HT(t)) * T2(NT \rightarrow HT)$$

or in a more general form:

$$(Eq. 5) \quad HT(Eq) = HT * T1 + (1 - HT) * T2$$

Resolving this for HT gives us:

$$(Eq. 6) \quad HT(Eq) = \frac{T2}{(1-T1+T2)}$$

This implies that only from the knowledge of two transition rates ($T1$ and $T2$) we can compute a steady state. It is important to note that the steady state will be reached sooner or later, regardless of the starting point of HT (which can have some value in the range of 0 to 1), as long as transition rates remain stable and do not vary systematically over time.

For the transition rates in the example above, we can compute a steady state rate of:

$$(Eq. 7) \quad HT(Eq) = \frac{0.15}{(1-0.70+0.15)} = 0.333$$

Result in the example: At a steady state of 33.3% Holiday Travelers in the population and constant transition rates of 0.70 (T1) and 0.15 (T2), the model will result in 33.3% of Holiday Travelers in the next period.

3 DATA

3.1 Data source

Data source for this paper is the annual „Reiseanalyse“ (RA), commissioned by *Forschungsgemeinschaft Urlaub und Reisen* (FUR) and implemented by *Institut für Tourismus- und Bäderforschung in Nordeuropa* (NIT) and *IPSOS Germany* (Schmücker & Koch 2014)

The dataset holds data from more than 7,000 face-to-face interviews surveyed each January. Data are representative for the German speaking (since 2011) or German (until 2010) population in private households aged 14 years and above. For this analysis, only the subset of Germans has been used to obtain a stable universe over time. Interviews are being carried out each year in January covering holiday trips with a duration of five days or more during the previous twelve months.

3.2 Holiday Travel Propensity

Holiday Travel Propensity (HTP) is the share of the population which took at least one holiday travel of five days or longer during the last twelvemonths.

Empirical HTP has grown from the 1950s through the mid-1990s and since then has shown stability on a level of slightly more than 75% with a peak of 77.3% in 2013 (Figure 2). Variation in the last decade was low (Lohmann, Schmücker and Sonntag 2014).

Applying a polynomial regression model to the data of the 60 years since 1954 (using 1954 as year 1 and 2013 as year 60) reveals a linear growth of 1.775 percentage points per year, corrected by a quadratic term of -0.013 per year², with an R² of .969 (Figure 2). This quadratic regression function will reach a maximum of 79.8% in 2021.

$$(Eq. 8) \quad HTP_{(t=1-60)} = 19.265 + 1.775t - 0,013t^2$$

[Figure 2 about here]

Within the annual Reiseanalyse, interviewees are asked to indicate whether they took a holiday travel in the year before the interview (which gives the HTP values indicated above), the previous year and the pre-previous year. For example, in January 2014 (RA 2014), interviewees are asked if they made a holiday travel in 2013 (period t), 2012 (t-1) and in 2011 (t-2).

For this analysis, we change the perspective and take the Holiday Travelers and Non Travelers of the year 2012 (t) and ask if they made a holiday travel in 2013 (t+1) or not. This will give us the transition rates needed for the analysis (Table 1).

Table 1: Transition matrix 2012-2013 for the German population 14+ years

	HT in 2012		NT in 2012		Total	
	Million	%	Million	%	Million	%
HT in 2013	43.71	92.1	5.77	34.8	14.66	22.7
NT in 2013	3.77	7.9	10.79	65.2	49.88	77.3
Total	47.48	100.0	16.56	100.0	64.55	100.0

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, n > 7,154, data source: RA 2014

3.3 Transition Rates

For the analysis we need two transition rates: Firstly, the share of Holiday Travelers in t travelling in t+1 (we designate this transition rate as “T1”) and the share of Non Travelers in t travelling in t+1 (“T2”). The way of computation for the two values has been shown above.

The values for T1 are remarkably stable over the last decade, with a minimum of 89.1 and a maximum of 91.1, a mean of 90.7 and a standard deviation of 1.0 (Table 2). Variation is showing a very slight *upward* trend, in a linear regression model the slope is 0.22 percentage points per year².

Variation in T2 is higher, with a minimum of 32.6 and a maximum of 46.2, a mean of 36.7 and a standard deviation from the mean of 4.1. Variation is showing a *downward* trend with a slope of – 0.75 percentage points per year.

Altogether, HTP values have slightly increased over the last decade, with a slope in the linear regression model of +0.11 percentage points per year.

Table 2: Transition rates for the years 2001 – 2012

t	HT in t > HT in t+1 T1	NT in T > HT in t+1 T2	Resulting HT in t+1 HTP	Source
2001	90.7	46.2	75.3	RA 2003
2002	89.8	42.8	76.8	RA 2004
2003	89.1	36.9	74.4	RA 2005
2004	90.3	33.1	73.6	RA 2006
2005	89.9	33.0	74.7	RA 2007
2006	89.4	38.9	74.8	RA 2008
2007	91.4	39.0	76.2	RA 2009
2008	90.9	34.9	75.7	RA 2010
2009	91.5	32.6	75.1	RA 2011
2010	91.9	33.6	75.3	RA 2012
2011	91.6	35.0	75.9	RA 2013
2012	92.1	34.8	77.3	RA 2014
Mean	90.7	36.7	75.4	
Std. Deviation	1.0	4.1	1.0	
Linear Regression Model				
Slope	+ 0.22	- 0.75	+ 0.11	
R ²	0.602	0.405	0.153	

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, n > 7,000 for every year, in %, data source: RA 2003 – RA 2014

² R² values are not discussed because they are of very limited relevance in this type of time series analysis. R² indicates how much of the variation in the dependent variable, relative to its mean, can be explained by the independent variable. If, however, values of the dependent variable are mostly stable over time (as required by the transition analysis), their variation is close to zero and thus a small R² value has little meaning. For the same reason, F values and their corresponding p levels have been omitted.

3.4 Steady state

Using the mean values from the table above would yield a HTP steady state:

$$(Eq. 9) \quad HTP(Eq) = \frac{0.367}{(1-0.907+0.367)} = 0.798$$

A first result of this paper therefore is, that Holiday Travel Propensity in the German population would reach its steady state at 79.8%, given that transition rates remain constant at the average level of the last decade. In other words: The HTP value for a given year might be above or below that equilibrium, but as long as transition rates remain stable, in the long run the equilibrium point will be reached. Interestingly, 79.8% is also very close to the maximum derived from the polynomial regression formula discussed above.

Actually, the HTP values are slightly below 79.8%, indicating that from a model point of view, HTP still has some room on the upside, although that room is very limited.

3.5 Equilibrium is not a threshold

Obviously, equilibrium in a Markov process is not an absolute threshold. Firstly, as we use survey data with a sampling error, we have to take sample variation into account.

Secondly, even if transition rates are stable, an intervention in a given period might temporarily change the result of the model. Imagine that the authorities introduce a cash back scheme during the main holiday planning period offering every inhabitant a sum of money to be used for holiday travel (in reality, such cash backs do exist e.g. in the form of refunds from tax or social security, although their use for holiday travel is of course not compulsory). This would probably lead to a holiday travel propensity that could go considerably beyond 80%, at least in the year in which the intervention takes place. However, if transition rates are not affected systematically (but only the state in the given period), the system will return to equilibrium in the following periods (this is why deciders, if they want to change systems, should try to influence transition rates rather than states).

3.6 Why have we not yet reached the equilibrium?

Modeling the Markov process over time (i.e., from year to year or generation to generation) with the transition rates T1 and T2 used above would reach the equilibrium after 12 years, even if starting with an HT value of 0. Reality, however, has taken much longer to reach a level of only 75%, while the equilibrium of 79.8% has not been reached until now

For this delayed development we can find a number of reasons.

Firstly, transition rates have not been stable since the 1950s, but only within the last decade or so. And even there we can still see an, although slight, increase in the T1 values, which in effect “pushes the frontier” a bit (Table 2). If we would e.g. take the transition rates derived from the survey of the year 2005 (T1 = 89.1%, T2 = 36.9%), the steady state would be at 77.2%, an HTP value that is very close to the value actually measured in the survey of the year 2014 (77.3%).

Secondly, we have to take into account, that sampling errors can occur. The sampling error is dependent on the level of confidence (a t value describing the number of standard deviations in a standardized normal distribution for the desired confidence level, e.g. $t=1.96$ for 95%), the share of the attribute we look at (p in %) and sample size (n)³. Within a 95% confidence level, the true value of HTP for the year 2013 is between $77.3-0.9 = 76.4$ and $77.3+0.9 = 78.2\%$.

$$(Eq. 10) \quad Error = \pm t * \sqrt{\frac{p*(100-p)}{n}} = \pm 1.96 * \sqrt{\frac{77.3*(100-77.3)}{7,795}} = \pm 0.93$$

Thirdly and most importantly, as mentioned above, a Markov equilibrium is neither a threshold nor an automatism. Specifically, factors influencing the state in any given year might lead to variation in the model result. In this case we would assume that in every year there are some unknown factors which, as a result, lead to a lower HTP value than predicted by the model.

All three factors together might explain why the actual HTP values, as measured in a large face-to-face sample every year, are still below the theoretical value calculated based upon the Marky chain.

3.7 Predictions and sub-group analysis

The predictive value of a Markov analysis lies mainly in the assumption that the system will reach a steady state as long as transitions rates are stable. This, however, is not an automatism, as shown above. In reality, transition rates are usually not stable, but show some variation depending on the development of social, demographic, economic or other environmental variables (“influencing factors”).

In order to improve the predictive value of the analysis it is therefore useful to look for influencing factors which on the one hand show different transition rates today and which we can assume to change in size over time in the future.

Usually, researchers would simply assess the development of the trait they are interested in (HTP, in this case) in the past under the groups of the influencing factor, would make assumptions on its future development in every subgroup and simply multiply this assumed value by the expected group size at some point in time in the future (this is the method applied for the same dataset in Lohmann, Schmücker and Sonntag 2014).

In an analysis of Markov equilibriums, however, such assumptions are not necessary, because the equilibrium value already has some predictive value (because this is the point the system should reach sooner or later as long as transition rates are stable). If transition rates are not stable, it might, at least in some cases, be easier to make assumptions on the development of transition rates as opposed to assumptions on the resulting trait. Therefore, at least some additional insights might be expected from this sort of analysis.

3.7.1 Age Group Analysis

One of such influencing factors could be age, because we see different transition rates in the age groups today and we can assume that the groups sizes will change in the future with a growth in older age groups and a decrease in the younger age groups.

³ In this case we do not control for population size because population is about 8,000 times larger than the sample.

Table 3 shows the development of HTP values over the last decade. We see that the slope of HTP in a linear regression model has increased in all age groups, although the increase is close to zero in the age group “60-69 years”.

Table 4 shows the equilibrium points derived from the transition rates. Here, we can see that for the younger age groups (up to 59 years) the equilibrium has a positive slope in a linear regression model, but in the two oldest age groups, the equilibrium point has slightly *fallen* over time.

Table 3: HTP values of age groups

in %	All age groups	14 - 19 years	20 - 29 years	30 - 39 years	40 - 49 years	50 - 59 years	60 - 69 years	70years or older
RA 2003	75.3	80.4	77.6	77.6	78.1	78.5	77.1	59.2
RA 2004	76.8	83.1	77.2	78.5	81	80.4	75.9	63.1
RA 2005	74.4	72.6	75.3	77.1	76.0	78.5	79.3	59.8
RA 2006	73.6	75.7	74.2	77.6	76.0	75.9	75.4	60.3
RA 2007	74.7	74.6	74.7	79.3	77.0	75.5	78.3	62.3
RA 2008	74.8	78.9	74.8	78.1	76.6	78.9	77.1	60.4
RA 2009	76.2	81.4	75.1	81.5	80.1	77.3	78.0	61.6
RA 2010	75.7	79.2	76.3	77.9	80.7	78.7	78.1	60.2
RA 2011	75.1	81.3	74.1	77.7	79.3	79.9	75.8	61.2
RA 2012	75.3	77.7	74.9	78.6	81.1	76.8	77.8	62.3
RA 2013	75.9	83.4	77.0	79.7	81.7	78.5	77.7	59.1
RA 2014	77.3	84.0	78.5	82.2	81.4	80.5	76.6	63.8
Mean	75.4	79.4	75.8	78.8	79.1	78.3	77.3	61.1
SD	1.0	3.5	1.4	1.5	2.1	1.6	1.1	1.5
Slope	+ 0.11	+ 0.43	+ 0.03	+ 0.25	+ 0.38	+ 0.07	+ 0.01	+ 0.11
R ²	0.153	0.180	0.007	0.317	0.386	0.026	0.001	0.068

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, n > 7,000 for every year, data source: RA 2003 – RA 2014

Table 4: Equilibrium values from simple Markov models in various age groups

Equilibrium (E) in %	14 - 19 years	20 - 29 years	30 - 39 years	40 - 49 years	50 - 59 years	60 - 69 years	70 years or older
RA 2003	85.2	86.2	85.4	84.9	85.2	83.5	67.6
RA 2004	85.7	80.4	82.2	85.3	83.6	77.7	65.7
RA 2005	78.6	78.7	81.9	78.1	79.3	81.3	55.2
RA 2006	78.1	79.6	82.7	78.3	76.3	79.2	62.9
RA 2007	74.9	78.6	83.6	80.0	74.1	77.7	58.5
RA 2008	83.5	78.2	82.1	81.0	82.7	80.9	57.2
RA 2009	84.5	83.7	88.2	85.2	79.1	83.0	62.7
RA 2010	83.5	81.0	79.4	85.2	82.2	81.7	57.9
RA 2011	85.2	78.8	82.5	82.6	83.4	77.1	62.3
RA 2012	80.9	81.7	85.7	85.0	81.6	83.7	59.2
RA 2013	87.0	83.2	85.3	87.2	81.7	79.2	55.9
RA 2014	88.9	82.9	87.7	85.6	83.7	77.2	62.9
E (Means)	83.1	81.1	83.8	83.2	81.3	80.4	60.9
Mean (E)	83,0	81,1	83,9	83,2	81,1	80,2	60,7
SD (E)	3.9	2.4	2.5	3.0	3.1	2.4	3.7
Slope (E)	+ 0.45	+ 0.06	+ 0.25	+ 0.40	+ 0.13	- 0.12	- 0.39
R ² (E)	0.160	0.008	0.126	0.218	0.021	0.032	0.128

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, n > 7,000 for every year, data source: RA 2003 – RA 2014

This was not expected because HTP values show a slightly *upward* slope for all age groups, as shown above. Although T1 values for these age groups have increased over the last decade (Table 5), T2 values have fallen even stronger and thus seem to over-compensate the rise in T1 (Table 6).

Table 5: T1 values of age groups (HT in t, HT in t+1)

in %	All age groups	14 - 19 years	20 - 29 years	30 - 39 years	40 - 49 years	50 - 59 years	60 - 69 years	70 years or older
RA 2003	90.7	89.5	91.1	91.1	91.1	92.2	91.1	87.0
RA 2004	89.8	90.4	86.1	89.2	90.9	91.7	90.6	88.4
RA 2005	89.1	89.0	86.1	89.8	88.1	91.5	92.1	85.4
RA 2006	90.3	86.7	89.4	91.4	90.5	91.4	92.6	87.3
RA 2007	89.9	85.4	88.6	91.3	90.9	90.8	91.3	87.8
RA 2008	89.4	89.2	86.8	89.3	90.4	92.6	91.6	84.3
RA 2009	91.4	88.1	91.2	93.4	92.4	90.9	93.3	87.9
RA 2010	90.9	89.6	89.3	88.1	93.2	92.8	93.6	87.7
RA 2011	91.5	91.6	89.3	90.2	92.5	93.2	92.8	89.6
RA 2012	91.9	87.1	90.1	93.5	93.4	92.7	93.7	89.8
RA 2013	91.6	92.0	90.8	91.8	93.8	92.5	92.0	87.3
RA 2014	92.1	93.5	89.3	94.2	93.5	93.2	92.3	88.6
Mean	90.7	89.3	89.0	91.1	91.7	92.1	92.3	87.6
SD	1.0	2.2	1.7	1.8	1.6	0.8	1.0	1.5
Slope	+ 0.22	+ 0,28	+ 0,20	+ 0,25	+ 0,38	+ 0,14	+ 0,16	+ 0,19
R ²	0.602	0.192	0.155	0.228	0.650	0.356	0.348	0.185

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, n > 7,000 for every year, data source: RA 2003 – RA 2014

Table 6: T2 values of age groups (NT in t, HT in t+1)

in %	All age groups	14 - 19 years	20 - 29 years	30 - 39 years	40 - 49 years	50 - 59 years	60 - 69 years	70years or older
RA 2003	46.2	60.6	55.8	52.1	50	44.9	45.2	27.1
RA 2004	42.8	57.7	57.0	49.8	52.6	42.4	32.8	22.2
RA 2005	36.9	40.3	51.3	46.0	42.4	32.5	34.3	18
RA 2006	33.1	47.5	41.4	41.2	34.3	27.7	28.1	21.5
RA 2007	33.0	43.6	41.9	44.4	36.3	26.3	30.4	17.2
RA 2008	38.9	54.7	47.4	49,0	40.8	35.3	35.6	21
RA 2009	39.0	64.9	45.1	49.2	43.7	34.5	32.7	20.3
RA 2010	34.9	52.8	45.7	46.0	39.0	33.2	28.6	16.9
RA 2011	32.6	48.5	39.7	46.2	35.6	34.1	24.3	17.2
RA 2012	33.6	54.5	44.2	39.1	37.4	32.4	32.4	14.8
RA 2013	35.0	53.4	45.5	47.6	42.3	33.4	30.5	16.1
RA 2014	34.8	52	52	41.3	38.6	34.8	26.1	19.3
Mean	36.7	52.5	47.3	46.0	41.1	34.3	31.8	19.3
SD	4.1	6.6	5.4	3.8	5.4	5.0	5.2	3.2
Slope	- 0.75	+ 0,03	- 0,68	- 0,55	- 0,82	- 0,49	- 0,95	- 0,65
R ²	0.405	0.000	0.191	0.255	0.281	0.117	0.404	0.486

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, n > 7,000 for every year, data source: RA 2003 – RA 2014

As a result we see more differentiation in older age groups than in younger age groups: While those travelling tend to travel in the next year as well (with comparable rates to other age groups), those who do not travel tend to stay at home in the next year (and that more often than in other age groups). This might be explained by the fact that in older age groups the physical or economical resources allowing people to travel tend to part those who can travel and those who can't more strictly than in younger age groups.

We also see that in the oldest age group actual HTP values are slightly above the expected equilibrium while in all other age groups actual values are slightly below expected equilibrium.

3.7.2 Health status

Although we do not have data on the holiday travel propensity and the actual health status (as being objectively assessed by some medical experts) from a single source, we have some data on the self reported health status, although not for every year in the past decade. Therefore, we are showing data from January 2006, January 2011 (five years later) and January 2014 (the most recent data available).

Table 7 shows the distribution of four subgroups, those reporting to be of excellent health (“I am completely healthy”), good health (“I am of good health, not counting for some minor discomforts”), moderate health (“I am somewhat restricted by my personal health status”) and poor health (“I am severely restricted by my personal health status”). We see only slight variation of the self reported health status within the last eight years. The extreme groups (excellent health and poor health) have slightly decreased while the two middle groups have slightly increased in importance.

Table 8 shows the development of HTP in the German population and the four subgroups. We see that HTP values are correlating to the four health status groups and are highest in the excellent health groups and lowest in the poor health group. Furthermore, HTP has decreased in the “poor health” group and increased in all other groups, with the highest increase rate in the “excellent health” group.

Table 7: Self-reported health status in German population

in %	Jan. 2006	Jan. 2011	Jan. 2014
excellent health	45.9	43.7	43.9
good health	33.9	36.0	35.4
moderate health	14.5	14.7	15.6
poor health	4.9	4.7	4.1
no answer	0.8	0.8	1.0

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, n > 7,000 for every year, data source: RA 2006, 2011, 2014

Table 8: Holiday Travel Propensity (HTP) in self-reported health status groups

in %	All groups	excellent health	good health	moderate health	poor health
RA 2006	73.6	79.8	76.3	59.7	36.6
RA 2011	75.1	81.1	79.6	58.6	35.7
RA 2014	77.3	85.2	79.8	61.0	32.6

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, n > 7,000 for every year data source: RA 2006, 2011, 2014

It is to be expected that health status and age correlate in a negative way. Thus, analyzing health status is more an addition to the analysis of age groups and similar results can be expected (Table 9). When performing the transition-equilibrium computations introduced above, we see that in the “poor health” group the HTP values are not only smaller than in other groups but also that the HTP value is practically identical to the calculated equilibrium value, which might be an indicator that in this group an equilibrium has been reached while in other groups equilibrium levels have not yet been reached (Table 10).

Table 9: Health status in different age groups

in %	All age groups	14 - 19 years	20 - 29 years	30 - 39 years	40 - 49 years	50 - 59 years	60 - 69 years	70years or older
excellent health	43.9	82.8	80.7	73.3	50.4	33.7	14.7	5.4
good health	35.4	12.2	15.1	21.2	40	46.9	50.9	42.5
moderate health	15.6	3.5	2.9	3.9	7.2	14.9	27	38.7
poor health	4.1	1	0.4	0.5	1.7	3.3	5.9	12.4

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, n = 7,154, data source: RA 2014

Table 10: Holiday Travel Propensity (HTP) in self-reported health status groups, RA 2014

in %	All groups	excellent health	good health	moderate health	poor health
T1	92.1	93.7	93.3	85.4	70.1
T2	34.8	50.2	36.1	21.1	14.4
Equilibrium	81.5	88.8	84.3	59.1	32.5
Actual HTP	77.3	85.2	79.8	61.0	32.6

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, n > 7,154, data source: RA 2014

4 EXTENSION: MATRIX WITH NINE ELEMENTS

Until now we have looked at transition matrices with two rows, two columns and thus four elements. An extension could be a matrix of more than two rows and columns and thus more than four elements. Although the computation of a unique equilibrium is somewhat more complex and sometimes not even possible, the general setup is identical to the four-elements-case.

For this paper we split the group of holiday travelers into those who took exactly one holiday travel and those who took more than one holiday travel. Again, we use time series data. Table 11 shows the base data, indicating that the share of non travelers and those taking more than one holiday travel has slightly decreased (negative slope in the linear regression model), while the share of people taking exactly one holiday travel has slightly increased.

Table 11: No, one and more than one holiday travels during the last twelve months

	No holiday travel during the last twelve months	One holiday travel during the last twelve months	More than one holiday travel in the last twelve months
Jan. 2003	24.7	57.7	17.7
Jan. 2004	23.2	57.2	19.6
Jan. 2005	25.6	55.0	19.4
Jan. 2006	26.4	55.3	18.3
Jan. 2007	25.3	56.3	18.4
Jan. 2008	25.2	58.3	16.5
Jan. 2009	23.8	58.9	17.2
Jan. 2010	24.3	57.7	17.9
Jan. 2011	24.9	57.9	17.2
Jan. 2012	24.7	57.9	17.4
Jan. 2013	24.1	59.2	16.7
Jan. 2014	22.7	61.0	16.2
Mean	24.58	57.70	17.71
SD	0.99	1.59	1.03
Slope	- 0.11	+ 0.32	- 0.22

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, $n > 7,000$ for every year, data source: RA 2003 – RA 2014

4.1 Transition rates

For the computation of equilibrium we need the transition rates in each of the three groups, resulting in a matrix with nine elements (Table 12). Again, as in the four-elements-case, we use average transition rates for the eleven years available in the dataset. The way the transition rates are derived from survey data is exactly the same as described above. Although transition rates are not exactly fix over time, their variation and slope is very limited.

Table 12 shows an overall plausible picture: Transition rates from 0 to 2+ holiday travels and vice versa are very low, the main diagonal has the highest values and the whole matrix is well balanced around its center. Illustratively, it seems that people who do not travel in one year will rarely compensate this by more than one holiday travel in the subsequent year.

Table 12: Average transition rates for eleven years

in %	No holiday travel in t	One holiday travel in t	More than one holiday travel in t
No holiday travel in t+1	63.3	11.3	3.1
One holiday travel in t+1	34.4	78.7	31.4
More than on e holiday travel in t+1	2.3	10.0	65.5

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, n > 7,000 for every year, data source: RA 2003 – RA 2014

Table 13 indicates that during the last eleven years transition rates have slightly increased in the main diagonal for the first two columns, thus stabilizing the effects described above.

Table 13: Slopes of transition rates for eleven years

Slope values (linear regression model)	No holiday travel in t	One holiday travel in t	More than one holiday travel in t
No holiday travel in t+1	+ 0.8	- 0.2	- 0.1
One holiday travel in t+1	- 0.6	+ 0.7	+ 0.4
More than on e holiday travel in t+1	- 0.1	- 0.5	- 0.4

Base: German population 14 years and older in private households in Germany, n > 7,000 for every year, data source: RA 2003 – RA 2014

4.2 Equilibrium

Finding equilibrium values for a matrix larger than four elements requires solving a system of linear equations. In our case, we can derive the equation 11 for the cases NHT (no holiday travel), 1HT (one holiday travel) and 2HT (two or more holiday travels) from the transition matrix which is graphically represented in Figure 3.

[Figure 3 about here]

$$(Eq. 11) \quad \begin{bmatrix} 0.633 & 0.113 & 0.031 \\ 0.344 & 0.787 & 0.314 \\ 0.023 & 0.100 & 0.655 \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} NHT(t) \\ 1HT(t) \\ 2HT(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} NHT(t + 1) \\ 1HT(t + 1) \\ 2HT(t + 1) \end{bmatrix}$$

We will use x , y and z for NHT, 1HT and 2HT, respectively, to keep equations shorter.

$$\begin{aligned} 0.633x + 0.113y + 0.031z &= x \triangleq -0.367x + 0.113y + 0.031z = 0 \\ \text{(Eq. 12)} \quad 0.344x + 0.787y + 0.314z &= y \triangleq 0.344x - 0.231y + 0.314z = 0 \\ 0.023x + 0.100y + 0.655z &= z \triangleq 0.023x + 0.100y - 0.345z = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Solving these systems (e.g. using Gauß's elimination procedure) will yield a steady state level of:

- No holiday travel (NHT): 20.3%
- One holiday travel (1HT): 60.7%
- Two or more holiday travels (2HT): 19.0%.

It should be noted, however, that these equation will not always be solvable in this way.

As shown in Table 11, transition rates have not been exactly fix during the last decade, but rather slightly decreasing for the two outer groups (no holiday travel and two or more holiday travels) and slightly increasing for the middle group (one holiday travel). Taking this into account, it is obvious that actual shares in the population might vary in the future without reaching the equilibrium points. However, it seems reasonable to assume that for the intensive traveler group (more than one holiday travels) there might still be one or two percentage points to be gained if only looking from a model perspective.

5 DISCUSSION

The paper has shown that the analysis of transition rates can be a simple and efficient way to estimate steady states of a system, provided it has approximately constant transition rates. In these cases, Markov chains have some advantages which can make them a valuable addition to other forecasting methods.

Firstly, the Markov chain analysis has a built in predictive value: It does not need assumptions on the development of influencing factors, but is able to abstract from these assumptions, at least to a certain degree. This reasoning is visible through the fact, that the knowledge of two transition rates is sufficient for a steady state estimation. No knowledge about the prior development is necessary. In its simplest form, a two step analysis can be performed. The paper shows, however, that also larger matrices can be analysed, although not in all cases a unique solution will emerge.

Secondly, the example of age groups or health groups has shown that with a Markov chain type analysis it is possible to differentiate between target groups or segments which have already reached or surpassed their steady state and those who didn't. This can be interpreted as an indicator for growth potential.

It must be clearly indicated, however, that the method has some restrictions. From a more theoretical point of view, the steady state is not an automatism and real data show that error terms can have a relatively large influence. The most important reason for errors might be found in the fact that stable transition rates will hardly be found in reality. From a practical viewpoint, a limitation might be, that data delivering transition rates must be available. Ideally, these transition rates will be drawn from longitudinal studies. In the datasets used for this analysis however, transition rates could be derived from cross-sectional surveys by reversing the perspective.

6 REFERENCES

- Beaman, J, Huan, TC & Kozak, M 2001, 'Estimating a Markov Model That Incorporates First Visit Decisions and Varying Repeat Frequency', *Tourism Analysis*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 81-97
- Behrends, E 2000, *Introduction to Markov Chains*. Vieweg, Wiesbaden
- Brémaud, P 1999, *Markov Chains. Gibbs Fields, Monte Carlo Simulation, and Queues*. Springer, New York (NY)
- Choi, JG, Mok, JW & Han, JS 2011, 'The use of Markov chains to estimate destination switching and market share', *Tourism Economics*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 1181-1196
- Crouch, G 1994, 'The study of international tourism demand: a review of practice', *Journal of Travel Research*, Vol. 33, pp. 41-54
- Frechtling, D 2001, *Forecasting Tourism Demand*. Routledge, Oxford
- Gantmacher, FR 1960, *Matrix Theory, Vol. 1*. Chelsea, Providence (RI)
- Geurts, MD, Buchman, TA & Ibrahim, IB 1976, 'Use of the Box-Jenkins Approach to Forecast Tourist Arrivals', *Journal of Travel Research*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 5-8
- Li, G, Song, H & Witt, SF 2005, 'Recent developments in econometric modeling and forecasting', *Journal of Travel Research*, vol. 44, pp. 82-99
- Lim, C 1999, 'A Meta analysis review of international tourism demand', *Journal of Travel Research*, vol. 37, pp. 273-278
- Lohmann, M, Schmücker, D & Sonntag U 2014, *German Holiday Travel 2025: Development of holiday travel demand in the German source market (The Reiseanalyse trend analysis)*, FUR, Kiel
- Mednick, H 1975, 'A Markov Chain Model of Travel Patterns of U. S. Visitors to Ontario', *Journal of Leisure Research*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 246-255
- Schmücker, D & Koch, A 2014, *Reiseanalyse 2014: Summary of the findings of the RA 2014 German Holiday Survey*, FUR, Kiel
- Seriola, B 2013, *Markov Chains: Theory and Applications*. Wiley, London
- Smeral, E, Witt, SF & Witt, CA 1992, 'Econometric Forecasts: Tourism Trends to 2000', *Annals of Tourism Research*, vol. 19, pp. 450-466
- Song, H & Li, G 2008, 'Tourism demand modelling and forecasting – A review of recent research', *Tourism Management*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 203-220
- Song, H, Smeral, E, Li, G & Chen JL 2008, *Tourism Forecasting: Accuracy of Alternative Econometric Models Revisited*. WIFO Working Papers, No. 326. Vienna
- Tsionas, EG & Assaf AG 2014, 'Short-run and long-run performance of international tourism: Evidence from Bayesian dynamic models', *Annals of Tourism Research*, vol. 42, pp. 22-36
- Uysal, M & Crompton, JL 1985, 'An Overview of Approaches Used to Forecast Tourism Demand', *Journal of Travel Research*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 7-15
- Waner, S & Costenoble, S 2013, *Finite Mathematics*. 6th ed., Brooks Cole, Stamford (CT)
- Wang, CH 2004, 'Predicting tourism demand using fuzzy time series and hybrid grey theory', *Tourism Management*, vol. 25, pp. 367-374
- Witt, SF & Witt, CA 1995, 'Forecasting tourism demand: A review of empirical research', *International Journal of Forecasting*, vol. 11, pp. 447-475
- Xia, J, Zeephongsekul, P & Arrowsmith, C 2009, 'Modelling spatio-temporal movement of tourists using finite Markov chains', *Mathematics and Computers in Simulation*. vol. 79, no. 5, pp. 1544-1553

Xia, J, Zeepongsekul, P & Packer, D 2010, 'Modelling spatio-temporal Movement using Semi-Markov Chains', *Tourism Management*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 844-851